

THE IMPACT OF TIPPING IN A RESTAURANT ON THE GUEST EXPERIENCE

Griezer Fanni

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11218631>

Abstract. *This study aims to analyze the impact of tipping in a restaurant on a guest experience. The research focuses on the factors provided by many websites, including general background and economic impact. This topic has been analyzed by collecting scholarly written studies and creating a survey about the observed topic to make a conclusion and recommendation to improve on 149 respondents' answers. It is looking for the answer to what importance tipping has and its economic background, how much guests are satisfied with the culinary experience, why they leave a bigger tip than usual, and what their overall opinion and reaction are in the world of tipping fatigue. After data analysis, tipping is considered as an appreciation of the service. A country's tipping culture may play a crucial role in its hospitality. For this reason and to respond to a lack of scholarly research and consider the outdated status of the available studies, this paper presents some solutions and highlights the importance of getting orientation about tipping culture when planning a trip. In this way, the country will be able to attract more tourists and foreign investors soon.*

Keywords: *tipping culture, restaurant, guest experience, satisfaction, reaction, appreciation.*

INTRODUCTION

“Tipping, or gratuity, is a sum of money given by a customer to appreciate the service provided by a worker” (indiatimes.com). It is given as an addition to the basic price of the service. The amount of the tip is based on how satisfied the guests are with the quality of the given service. Some countries do not define tips with a fixed percentage, since tipping may not be expected when a fee is explicitly charged for the service (indiatimes.com).

Tipping custom has a long history, but its origin is still disputed. One source mentions it has no clear origin, but most probably it was primarily practiced in Tudor England from the 15th century (investopedia.com). It came from Europe in the 15th century, but it was getting more popular in the United States in the 19th century (investopedia.com). The practice of tipping has roots in England, where waiters get extra money when they perform well.

Dr. Peters and Birardi both mentioned that a 20% tip is the minimum appropriate for the standard tipped workers and that larger tips (more than 20%) should be a sign of recognition for excellent customer service (cnbc.com).

From the middle of the 17th century, boxes started to be labeled “to insure promptness (TIP)” to award waiters for quick yet good service by guests in London coffee houses and other shops (investopedia.com).

This practice reached America from Europe. In the beginning, it was not well-received by Americans, as they saw it as unrelated to the values of a democratic society. What they say about the culture of appreciation and how their tipping, attitudes reflect wider aspects of society—the tipping aimed to establish social status by the elite.

In the 20th century, an anti-tipping demonstration started due to an undemocratic view which created a servant class. The first state that banned this manual was Washington in 1909,

followed by Arkansas, Iowa, South Carolina, Tennessee, and Georgia, but it ended in 1926, and since then tipping has flourished (bbc.co.uk).

The US is the most tip-friendly country all over the world, but there are huge international variations. "Tipping can be problematic because it seems to create classes, that of the customers, and that of the service workers, who have to satisfy the customers and sort of 'beg' for the tips," as Ofer Azar, a professor of behavioral economics, said.

Tipping started to be created to express appreciation for the quality of the food or the service or even the kindness of the waiter. Tipping got another function because the restaurant owners were unable to close the wage gap. While the first federal minimum wage law was passed in 1938, it was not until almost three decades later that the tip minimum wage was established. In 1991, the federal minimum wage for tipped employees was set at \$2.13, which is what it remains as of March 2023. The USA is the only country that exempts tipped workers from having to receive the full minimum wage. In 43 states, paying tipped workers less than the standard minimum wage is legal because tips presumably make up that difference (cnbc.com).

Nowadays service charges are inevitable for American diners because tipping has become a tradition in American dining culture and these places are not prepared for service-inclusive pricing (eater.com). Leaving gratitude is also used to show own financial status.

Methodology and data specification

A questionnaire was created where the goal was to map the motivation and the last experiences about eating out and to get to know the amount of tips the guests leave in a restaurant. This survey created on Google Surveys was sent to private groups on Facebook and group chats at Silk Road University.

"Tipping culture" was checked in Google Trends to get to know if tourists are informed about this policy or not. This website shows how many times and from which countries searched this word. For the last 12 months worldwide, the number of searches has been infinitesimal (under 100 until January 2024), but for the last 12 months from Uzbekistan, there has been no search at all.

Graph 1.: Searches for “tipping culture” in Google Trends worldwide for the last 12 months by interests, source: Google Trends

For searching by region, it is interesting to see Singapore was the only country where people searched for this keyword to get orientation in this rule. In the top 5 countries, Singapore is followed by Portugal, Canada, Ireland, and the United Arab Emirates with an amount less than half of the Singaporean amount.

After data cleaning, the number of respondents is 149, and the proportion of males and females is 30.2 and 69.8%. The age group of 16 to 30 years old represents 75.2% and of 31 to 50 years old is 18.8% of the total respondents. 41.7% of the respondents have bachelor's and 28.2% have master's degrees. These people are from 29 different countries, but the majority come from Hungary, Mexico, and Uzbekistan. The questionnaire is composed of four sections besides

Demographic data, such as Habits to eating out, Leaving a tip in a restaurant, Tipflation, and Effects of tipping culture.

Based on the answers for the first section, more than half of the respondents (51%) eat out once a month, 22.1% once a week, and 13.4% more than once a week. The frequency of the visit can be explained by the disposable income, the motivation, or the free time.

In general, they are satisfied with their last experience in a restaurant because, on a Likert scale, they score it between 3 and 5 beside one answer. They were amazed by the taste, variety, and quality of food, atmosphere, design, and service, but they explained the lack of the maximum score by the cleanliness and loudness of the place and they felt embarrassed when a waiter did not even know the menu.

The “Leaving a tip” section started with an association of a country that comes first to their mind if they hear “tipping”. The USA got the highest vote, which as discussed before even if the tipping itself started in England, it became more popular in the USA. Only 44.3% used to check how the tipping culture is in a destination when planning a trip, but knowing in advance about it in their next destination before arrival would help them avoid misunderstanding (50.3%) and it would be easier to figure out the budget (36.2%), “I appreciate when we know in advance that a service fee is included, so it means I do not have to worry about a tip after” says a respondent. A little bit less than this percentage, people would not feel influenced because of their stable financial background or their higher disposable income. The biggest amount of tip they left is an average of 13€, but the biggest 100€ and the least 0.5€ were both surprising.

They leave a bigger tip because of the expression of their satisfaction with the performance of the waiter (51%) and their appreciation of the whole culinary experience (28.2%). It happens the least that they leave a tip because of the quality of the food, which refers to Japanese cuisine where a good quality of food is fundamental, so tipping is kind of a rude action.

What is the main reason if you leave a bigger tip than usual?
 149 válasz

Graph 2: Reasons for leaving a bigger tip than usual, source: own questionnaire

They were asked to put the tipping functions in order. In daily life, more than two-thirds leave a tip as a sign of appreciation for the service, more than 50% for the quality of the food and 31% just take into account the fact that the waiters’ salary is quite low and for this reason they endeavor to compensate it.

As for the “Tipflation” part, when paying the bill and the restaurant provides options with different amounts of tips. This action stresses out 35% of respondents and 18% do not know how to react. If people are not informed by themselves or by the service provider, it creates a lot of embarrassing moments for both sides, one said “I always choose 0%, because it makes me mad. I tip when I am satisfied.” This feedback is represented by 36.9%, but 10% tip more. In this situation, they are willing to pay 10% (43.6%) and 5% (21.5%) of the bill as a tip.

If when paying the bill, the restaurant provides you options with different amount of tips, how does it influence you?
149 válasz

Graph 3: Influence of digital screen on tipping, source: own questionnaire

Overall, 54.4% consider tipping culture as a form of appreciation, 31.5% as stressing out and 26.8% think it can be a way to round up the underpayment of the workers in this field. This action affects restaurants by giving a chance to round up the underpayment of the workers (45%), to make the service more attractive (42.3%), or to create connections between the waiters and the clients (20.1%). More than 10% shared their opinion about discouragement of dining in.

Key findings

Leaving a tip has many functions, such as showing the financial status, appreciating the given service, or completing the waiters' wages, but based on the answers of respondents first, it means the appreciation of the service, secondly completing the salary of the waiter, thirdly being in accordance with expectations of the society, and last but not least it represents the own financial status.

After the introduction of tipping, tourism and hospitality were not the same anymore. 53.7% think it provided a possibility for the workers to get extra money, 43% say it makes the bill more expensive and for 25.5% it has a meaning of a higher level of service.

51% eat out once a month and they were satisfied with the last experience, mainly for the taste, variety, and quality of food, the atmosphere and design of the place, and the service, but it also happened if the interior was not clean enough or if they felt embarrassed when a waiter cannot give the real professionalism.

Policy implications and conclusion

Every country has its own rules for gratuities, they are so divergent, that is why, it's important to consider other cultures and respect them when traveling. For this reason, researching local tipping customs is highly recommended to avoid inconveniences: some expect tips, but some feel offended by being tipped.

If the staff is fully compensated by its salary, the gratuities are not needed. The unification of tipping is not possible all around the world due to the diverse standard of living, but raising the salary can be a good way not to focus on extra tips to complete the wage. Tipping culture increases productivity, but it should be achieved by a higher wage, thus creating a clear picture of how much the restaurant values its staff.

If there are not enough resources to provide it to them, at least the countries should make sure the customers are aware of tipping before their arrival.

Research questions are answered by explaining the importance of tipping and its economic background. The functions of tipping were understood and the impacts of the expansion of digital tipping generated the new phenomenon called tipflation was discussed.

Tipping was introduced to appreciate the culinary experience, but over the years it created a possibility to decrease the salary of the workers under the minimum wage and make up the difference.

There are some advantages and disadvantages to tipping. With tips, some workers can earn more than the regular minimum wage, and restaurant owners who provide the tipping minimum wage can keep their prices and costs down, but servers who rely on tips for income can get insufficient salaries. If restaurant owners pay their staff the regular minimum wage, it is on the cards to increase the prices of their goods and services to balance labor expenses (What importance does tipping have?).

Based on the results of the survey, guests are satisfied with the culinary experience, which is shown by the given scores when they were asked about their last eating-out experience (How much are guests satisfied with the culinary experience?). 45-45% scored it 4 and 5 out of 5.

Leaving a bigger tip than usual can be explained by the satisfaction with the performance of the waiter, which got 51%, but 28% tip better for the whole culinary experience (Why do they leave a bigger tip than usual?).

Tipping itself encourages workers to provide their best service to increase their tips, but a lot of answers were related to the fact that the waiters should not work for the extra money, but should be paid better.

In many cases, tips are not mandatory, and guests have the option to customize how much they tip, but it can be an embarrassing moment as well to leave tips for goods or if restaurants have a digital tipping system to “force” them to tip or if guests do not even know about the given tipping culture. Digital tipping makes feel guests bad because it stresses them out, sometimes they do not know how to react to it without seeing and tasting the food or experiencing the service and makes them tip more than usual (What is their overall opinion and reaction in the world of tipping fatigue?).

Definitely, it is worth diving into this topic deeper, because it is part of everybody’s life. The research can be extended to conduct interviews with different types of restaurants and make a comparison between them. Also, if different nations would be asked about the tipping, can be interesting.

REFERENCES

1. [bbc.com \(bbc.com/travel/article/20230606-how-to-tip-around-the-world\)](https://www.bbc.com/travel/article/20230606-how-to-tip-around-the-world)
2. [cnbc.com \(cnbc.com/select/new-tipping-culture-money-experts-weigh-in/\)](https://www.cnbc.com/select/new-tipping-culture-money-experts-weigh-in/)
3. [forbes.com \(forbes.com/advisor/business/digital-tipping-culture/\)](https://www.forbes.com/advisor/business/digital-tipping-culture/)
4. [investopedia.com \(investopedia.com/tipflation-8180832\)](https://www.investopedia.com/tipflation-8180832)
5. [johnlewisfinance.com \(johnlewisfinance.com/currency/tipping-culture-tips-around-the-world.html\)](https://www.johnlewisfinance.com/currency/tipping-culture-tips-around-the-world.html)
6. [westernunion.com \(westernunion.com/blog/en/global-tipping-guide/\)](https://www.westernunion.com/blog/en/global-tipping-guide/)